

The Commerce Education Role in Indian Economy Development

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Abstract:

Commerce education playing a significant role in strengthen economic systems by developing skilled human capital, promoting entrepreneurship and supporting financial and business institutions. This research article examines the commerce education role in economic development with help of the primary data collected from students and teachers of commerce. Using a structured questionnaire and simple statistical tools, the study analysis perceptions regarding employability, entrepreneurship, financial literacy and contribution to national economic growth. The finding reveal that commerce education significantly contributes to economic development by enhancing skills, employment opportunities and business efficiency. The research concludes with the suggestions for strengthening commerce education to meet the changing needs of the Indian economy.

Keywords: Commerce Education, Economic Development, Employability, Entrepreneurship, Human Capital

Introduction:

Education is an important component for economic and social development of a country, education plays essential role in economic growth. It is one of the decisive area which Leads to success in all sectors of the economy. Today public, private, corporate sector demand professional in their goal setting. Education is one of the most dynamic and investment attractive sector in the Indian market, the key role education requires a special relationship person by society and state, Commerce education has become backbone for development of business and national development, it covers wide zone of business and society. Commerce education imparts skill-oriented teaching to students. as Fredrick G. Nicholas described as “commerce education a type of training it plays important parts in the achievement of the general aim of education on any given levels for its primary objectives, for the preparation of students to step foot into the business career or entered in those career which render more effective service thereon and to advance from their present employment level to higher levels. In India every business has to perform Commerce as it is an activity to do. Commerce related to buying and selling of goods on a large scale basis. In brief,

Commerce is a combination study of accounts, business studies and economics. Commerce stands on 3 pillars. There is no business without commerce, Commerce provides stability in the organization, Direction, and most importantly it provides growth to the organization. Accounts subject helps the organization to see the true, fair, condition or picture of our business with the help of trading account, profit and loss account, balance sheets, journals, ledgers, etc. Economics one of the most vital aspects of commerce, it gives business knowledge on how to use limited resources at most effective level for business and to get maximum profit in short duration. Business studies gives knowledge about Human resource management, sales management, marketing, etc. That’s why there is no business without commerce, Commerce is a part of all the activities carried out in business, such as manufacturing, planning, advertising, etc. Sometimes business & commerce seem to be same, but it is different at some angle.

Commerce education plays crucial role in the development of the Indian economy, it helps in developing finance, accounting, managerial and analytical skills which required for trade, industry, banking, and taxation. Commerce education

encourages entrepreneurial thinking and risk-taking, it support trade, commerce and industry and development of financial system, and it opens diverse employment opportunities, helps in digital and e-commerce growth.

Statement of the Problem:

Education direct and indirectly impacts on national output, educated raise national income because schooling raises their marginal productivity. The positive effect of raising human capital on the productivity of physical capital requires to offset the reducing returns to investment in physical capital. Commerce education not away from numerous issues like Global competition in the market creating problems for commerce graduates in India, they are not getting sophisticated education. And there is a lack in infrastructure facilities like, no technology well- equipped classrooms with modern communication devices like a projectors, computer network, etc. Theory oriented method of teaching like syllabus adopted in UG and PG is more theoretical oriented and lacks in practical knowledge. In India, most of institution institutions are dependent on government funds and government grants becoming insufficient in providing good infrastructure and learning resources, which are must to provide world-class knowledge to students. Providing only general education is in the name of commerce education not enough. Many of them are failing to identify the opportunities that are availing to the commerce graduate. Commerce Education deficiency in employability skills and does not make the students to face the complex problem in business. Many of them are not able to think and make decisions their own; they think that commerce is not best for their career option so that they are moving towards medicine, engineering, IT courses. Despite the growing importance of commerce education, questions remain regarding its actual contribution to economic development. There is a need to empirically examine whether commerce education truly enhances employability, entrepreneurial skills and economic awareness

among learners. This study attempts to analyse the role of commerce education using primary data.

Objectives:

1. To study the concept and scope of the commerce education in India
2. To analyse the role of commerce education in inclusive growth of Indian economic activities.
3. To highlight the roles of commerce education in dynamic business world;
4. To give suggestion based on the findings of the study

Hypothesis:

H0: the opinion of professionals about the commerce education is equal to average level

H1: the opinion of professionals about commerce education is not equal to average

H0: the perception level of professionals on role of commerce education in Indian economy growth is equally distributed.

H1: the perception level of professionals on role of commerce education in Indian economy growth is equally distributed.

Literature Review:

Pratap et al., (2015) stated that the commerce students are exposing to the outside environment of the business of the world through. It also provides them guidance them in applying the principles whenever students do business. Commerce education gives positive attitude and confidence them. It ensures effective resources management, students also understanding the concept of savings, investment, and capital formation. He also mentioned lack in commerce that is commerce graduates not have practical knowledge.

Deswa (2017) he highlights that these days, commerce education is taking a new shape as professional approach and this change took place due to industrial and economic advancements. The change in technology provides reduce in the paperwork and new dimension. He also highlight

more on the education system. Any exchange of money, any transaction that happens all because of development of commerce.

However, we can sure that, without commerce education there is no business right from the schools. Unlike other subject science and arts, we can see different specialized courses but in commerce we can see marketing, finance accounting and taxation. Many students are not familiar with their specialized fields as the business and market is growing vast, there is a need of commerce with efficient commerce knowledge to those who can deal with all matters of business.

Heena tabasum and venkatesh (2021) argued that commerce education not only teaches theoretical understanding of business principles but also exposes and introduces students to real- world economic environments, helping them comprehend distribution channels, business decision-making and market systems. Their work emphasizes that commerce education contributes substantially to economic growth by creating professionals who understand trade and economic processes.

Brahmaniya and bhatt(2021) underlines that the commerce education plays a vital role in inclusive economic growth through providing learners with awareness of socio- economic principles and encouraging productive participation in markets.

Research Methodology:

Data Collected for study is collected from primary and secondary sources. Primary data has

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Hypothesis testing:

Null hypothesis: the opinion of professionals about commerce education is equal to average level

Table 1: t-test for specified value of statement “commerce education perception of professionals”

Statement on perception about commerce education	Mean	SD	T value
Commerce helps in transfer human being into human resource	3.90	1.07	16.776
It creates and provides many opportunities for future growth	4.10	1.03	21.291
It Increases the skills sets and knowledge	3.99	1.14	17.472
It contributes and helps for industrial development and growth of India	3.90	1.21	14.878

Note- the significance level at 1%.

been collected from distributing the questionnaire to sample respondents, who has graduation in commerce the total sample collected is 150 respondents by convenient sampling. Data analysed from SPSS software by using mean, standard deviation, chi-square test, and t-test. For secondary sources referred various journals, websites, research articles and magazines and other online information, social science census, information collected from various government departments, researcher analyse through secondary sources.

Concept and Scope of Commerce Education:

The Commerce education refers to systematic instruction in subjects related to business and economic activities. It includes disciplines such as accounting, finance, taxation, business law, economics, management, marketing, banking, insurance, auditing, and e-commerce

The scope of the commerce education in India has expanded due to

- Growth of trade and industry
- Expansion of the banking and financial sector
- Implementation of GST and modern taxation systems
- Emergence of digital business and finch
- Globalization of marketing

Commerce education prepares students for careers in business organisations, financial institutions, government departments and self-employment ventures.

The – value is below 1.01, so we rejected the null hypothesis at 1 % level of significance about the statement “the opinion of professionals about commerce education is equal to average level”. Hence the opinion regard to all professionals about commerce education is not equal to average level. From that we can that the commerce education certainly, helps in transform human

resources by imparting knowledge and skills. It contributes in industrial development and growth of India.

Hypothesis 2:

H0: the perception level of professionals in role of commerce education in Indian economy growth is equally distributed.

Table: 2 chi-square test for goodness of fit of equality of level the perception level of professionals in role of commerce education in Indian economy grow.

Level of perception on role of commerce education	Frequency	%	Chi-square value	P value
Low	3.90	25.5	44.180	<0.001
Moderate	4.10	49.0		
High	4.10	49.0		
Total	3.90	100		

Note: significance level at 1%.

From above table p-value is less than 0.01, so the null hypothesis is rejected at 1% significance level, so we can conclude that the perception level of professionals on role education in Indian economy growth is not equally distributed. From above data, the majority of professionals belong to

Findings:

- It is found that commerce education plays a crucial role in contributing to Indian economy growth through providing opportunity in the field of accountancy, finance, business, production and consumption.
- It is found that, commerce education vital for industry growth, but placement is quite low due to huge output.

Suggestions:

There is need to improve the infrastructure and learning resources in commerce education to tackle global challenges facilities such as communication devices like internet facilities, computer networks, business labs, overhead projectors, etc.

moderate group only (49.0%). As few professionals say, the role of commerce education on rowing Indian economy is low due to more output but less placement. Few opined that the commerce education role is high and it contributes in Indian economy growth.

One of the important recommendation for commerce education is that, it should provide not only theoretical oriented knowledge but, also should provide practical knowledge so they can easily face the competitive world, While constructing the syllabus, we should consider these things, syllabus should one which better in consult industrialists from various fields which are more relevant, Contextual, and industry-oriented.

Regular curriculum revision aligned with industry needs, integration of practical training, internships and case studies, emphasis on digital skills, data analytics, and financial technology, strong industry-academia collaboration, promotion of research and innovation in commerce education.

Conclusion:

India has the strategic advantage of the young population. Under the WTO regime, the

relevance of management education has become more imperative; it means huge changes in the ways commerce and management education persuasion in India. Therefore, it is necessary to make commerce graduation courses more effective. Commerce Education is facing numerous problems today. Moreover these problems have a direct impact on the course objectives and course contents. Therefore it is crucial for re-designing commerce education in such a way that to be relevant to today and tomorrow. Globalization has provided a wider scope of opportunities to our commerce undergraduate students and postgraduate students and also tackle the challenges to our commerce education of equipping our students with multiple skills to meet global job market that is expectations of all over the globe. However, commerce education has become the backbone of every country's economic system. There is strong demand in India and worldwide for graduates who developed the potential to take leadership roles in international business.

India will be excel in its talent management and knowledge management shortly if its' government puts hand together with the higher education sector for providing quality education to the students. By making commerce education relevant and practical oriented, and it may be global competitiveness to our students. Hence the role of Commerce Education in national development is should be well established.

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